

IMPROVEMENT OF URBAN ENVIRONMENT AND PROBLEMS OF URBAN DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This article provides information about the problems of urban planning and improving the urban environment.

Key words: City population, urban planning, urbanization, natural environment, residential buildings, city roads.

In the conditions of intensive urbanization, which has caused the rapid growth of cities and the concentration of people in a small area, along with the issues of protecting the natural environment from the harmful effects of urban influences, the tasks of creating and maintaining them are a full-fledged living environment in a complex urban mechanism. It is becoming more and more important. To improve the state of the urban environment surrounding a person, the improvement sub-sectors are important. Sanitation, cleaning of city roads and landscaping. However, there is a significant lag in their development, both in housing construction and in other sub-sectors of improvement. The problem of bringing the rate of housing and industrial construction closer to the rate of development of beautification is one of the most important tasks of urban planning. It is not enough to focus efforts only on the development of one of the improvement sub-sectors (creating the material and technical base, providing personnel, building individual improvement facilities, etc.), it is necessary to take into account their connection with other sectors. Improvement of facilities and creation of the appropriate operational background. It should be noted that the improvement elements of the considered sub-sectors (residential buildings, residential buildings, urban roads and other facilities) important requirements are not sufficiently taken into account in urban planning practice and design, and in the implementation of new construction, capital repair, reconstruction and use. At the same time, these requirements are not always clearly formulated and defined, to a small extent they are regulated by relevant decisions, norms and design rules. The most effective review of relevant requirements can be done during construction and reconstruction; At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the strength of serviced facilities, residential buildings, road network, landscaping systems, as well as the difficulty (sometimes impossibility) of their subsequent reconstruction. It is necessary to consider their interrelationship with each other and with other sub-sectors of improvement (road construction, sewerage, water supply, etc.). Separate building and at all stages of design and project implementation. Solving the problem of creating an appropriate operational background is largely determined not only by the existing architectural and planning solution of the city (agglomeration), the functional division of the territory, but also by the population and importance of the city, its development prospects, depending on climatic and other local conditions. The general requirements for the formation should be determined taking into account the local conditions of the operational background. Population is one of the main factors that make up the city and has a great influence on the level of improvement and development of the city. The development of new systems of settlements, cities and settlements implies the construction of new landscaping facilities and the reconstruction of existing ones.

Since the centralized improvement planning system mainly applies to cities and urban-type settlements, the dynamics of urban population growth is largely dependent on road cleaning, maintenance of improvement facilities, domestic areas, collection, removal and disposal of household waste. The rapid development of urbanization in the country leads to the complexity of the forms of urban settlements and the emergence of large urban agglomerations, the number of which is growing rapidly. Urban agglomeration means a compact territorial grouping of urban and rural settlements united in a complex dynamic system with various connections - industrial, communal, recreational, as well as joint use of a certain area and its resources. This requires a new approach to cleaning, sanitation and landscaping. When planning and implementing measures for the improvement of the considered networks, it is necessary to take into account the needs of not only the agglomeration center, but also the small towns and villages that are part of it. It is necessary to proceed from the needs, therefore, an ergonomic approach is used in the development of projects for small landscape and architectural forms. This involves taking into account anthropometric, sanitary-hygienic, emotional and psychological requirements. Anthropometric requirements based on the dimensions and proportions of the human body are taken into account when determining the height of stairs and handrails, the height and dimensions of tables and benches, the inclination of seats and backs, and the location of armrests. Dimensions of children's play equipment, etc. Thus, anthropometric data is based on the calculation of the dimensions of the stairs according to formula $4 \cdot b + 2p = 64$ cm, where b is the width of the stairs, taken outside the buildings at intervals of 34 to 40 cm and sometimes more; h - step height. When determining the width of pedestrian avenues and paths, anthropometric data is included - their width is taken as a multiple of the conditional section for one pedestrian - 75 cm. The comfort of the object-spatial environment in which sanitary-hygiene requirements are formed and safety conditions and regulates parameters such as temperature, physical and chemical composition of air, light, noise. It is important to take into account the sanitary-hygienic requirements during installation, etc. The microclimate is regulated taking into account the sanitary-hygienic requirements. A decrease in air temperature is ensured by the creation of water devices. The direction and speed of the wind is changed by modeling the terrain, creating screens and decorative walls from green areas. Taking into account the direction of the slopes allows adjusting the lighting conditions and the temperature of the earth's surface. Emotional and psychological requirements are related to the characteristics of information reception and processing by a person. They are taken into account when determining the color schemes of small landscape and architectural forms, choosing fonts for signs, depending on their "readability", choosing graphics based on the properties of different colors and their combinations. Information schemes that help you navigate space easily, etc. The role of beautification of the urbanized area in creating a comfortable living environment. The socialist planning system of the urban space formed during the period of directive economy based on the methods of vertical administrative management (urban planning) is incompatible with free market conditions. With the emergence of private ownership of real estate and the introduction of land plots into the market, a special mechanism of territorial development based on more flexible methods of regulation at the municipal level 5 was required.

The methods of city regulation introduced into the practice of municipal management are mainly related to the creation of attractive conditions for the implementation of new construction and the improvement of the efficiency of land use for commercial purposes. A business-oriented model of spatial development is emerging, which leads to the aggravation of socio-economic problems.

The problems of using transport and providing communal infrastructure in some cities. It is necessary to develop a socially oriented model that takes into account the interests of local communities, and its improvement will improve the effectiveness of spatial development. becomes the main criterion, which cannot be achieved by private investment and traditional mechanisms of market regulation of construction. Activity and urban planning require the development of special management methods and institutions within the boundaries of individual urban areas designated as .The transition to a market economy, problems of development of the city and urban space associated with the development of decentralization processes, the emergence of a special role of local state authorities in the management of territorial development (property market by regulating private investment activities) It was covered in the works of a number of scientists in the decade. Among them are the developments of well-known regional scientists of the Institute of Systematic Analysis of the Russian Academy of Sciences V.N. Lexina and A.N. Shvetsov. The works of V.L. Glazychev, engaged in the development of the urban environment (Academy of National Economy). The main and practical issues of urban regulation were also updated in the works of specialists of the Institute of Urban Economy, S.A. Bogolyubov, M.D. Safarova, E.K. Trutnev, etc. It occupies an important place among modern studies of the development of local societies. By the works of Kuban State University scientists TT Avdeeva and YV Filippov, founders of the Kuban school for the development of local communities. Research by A.A. Vysokovsky, A.E. Gutnova, S.N. Maksimova, A.B. Marchenko, O.A. Smirnova, E.I. Tarasevich and a number of other representatives of modern Russian economics are devoted to the problems of regulation of investment and construction activities, the real estate market, including the land market in cities, as the main object of the regulation of urban development activities carried out at the municipal level. Organizational and economic relations that arise in the course of private investment activities as the main factor of changing the urban space in the market economy P.L. studied in his works. Vilensky, I.L. Vladimirova, JI.H. Drobishevskaya, V.N. Liveshits.

Conclusion.

Modern principles of a systematic approach to the analysis and management of spatial urban systems V.I. Resins. Development patterns of the urban real estate market in the conditions of a transitional economy, creation of an effective tool for its analysis, problems of investment and construction project planning G.M. studied in his works. Sternik. It is worth noting the work devoted to the development of the concept of urban planning, the specialists of the Moscow Development Institute of the Municipal Fund T.M. Govorenkova, D.A. Savina. The transformation of real estate should not be considered as an investment project for the development of a single free plot of land, but as a project for the development of the territory, which will achieve convenience for all residents (not only for construction companies and owners of real estate objects that are being created). need This creates a transition to a socially oriented type of spatial development management, which requires a change in the methods of regulation at the boundaries of local urban areas. The development of local cities, whose methods are fundamentally different from real estate development, is both vacant and residential. -related to the transformation of the area, aimed at ensuring the widest range of external users of the local population and local area facilities. equal opportunities in the use of public goods and their equal quality. This allows us to connect the processes of spatial development of the city not only with the creation of new material objects of the urban environment, but also, first of all, with the creation of favorable conditions for the life and development of local communities.

It depends on the level of inclusion in the context of the general development, and on the compatibility of the changes in the material space with the changes in the social space. Urban development, as a mechanism of urban planning, is based on the principle of partnership - coordinated cooperation of many interested parties (local community stakeholders): authorities, entrepreneurs, landowners, representatives of various interests. Local territorial communities (users of capital construction objects, consumers of services from real estate objects, owners of existing real estate objects). The model of regulating the spatial development of the city based on the development of local cities has the following hierarchy of functions includes.

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